

Supplement-1: Funnel plot and Egger's test for publication bias on the effect of quercetin treatments on production, egg quality, blood metabolites, and anti-oxidant defence in laying hens. $P_{\text{egger}} < 0.05$ and asymmetry Funnel plots demonstrate high risk publication bias.